

Plain language summary of results from the JAVELIN Bladder 100 study: avelumab maintenance treatment for advanced urothelial cancer

Thomas Powles¹, Se Hoon Park², Eric Voog³, Claudia Caserta⁴, Begoña P Valderrama⁵, Howard Gurney⁶, Haralabos Kalofonos⁷, Sinisa Radulovic⁸, Wim Demey⁹, Anders Ullén¹⁰, Yohann Loriot¹¹, Srikala S Sridhar¹², Norihiko Tsuchiya¹³, Evgeny Kopyltsov¹⁴, Cora N Sternberg¹⁵, Joaquim Bellmunt¹⁶, Jeanny B Aragon-Ching¹⁷, Daniel P Petrylak¹⁸, Robert J Laliberte¹⁹, Bo Huang²⁰, Nuno Costa²¹, John A Blake-Haskins²² & Petros Grivas²³

First draft submitted: 22 December 2021; Accepted for publication: 9 March 2022; Published online: 13 April 2022

Summary

What is this summary about?

This is a plain language summary of an article originally published in *The New England Journal of Medicine*. It is about initial results (collected in October 2019) from the JAVELIN Bladder 100 study (a clinical trial), which looked at **avelumab** maintenance treatment in people with advanced **urothelial** cancer. **Urothelial** cancer is the most common type of bladder cancer. People with advanced **urothelial** cancer often receive **chemotherapy**. If this is the first treatment people with advanced disease are given, it is called first-line treatment. If the cancer stops growing or shrinks with first-line **chemotherapy**, people can be given different treatment to try to prevent the cancer from growing again. This is called maintenance treatment. It may help people live longer.

What happened in the JAVELIN Bladder 100 study?

In the JAVELIN Bladder 100 study, researchers wanted to find out if maintenance treatment with avelumab would help people with advanced urothelial cancer live longer. Avelumab is a type of medicine called immunotherapy. Immunotherapy helps the body's immune system fight cancer. 700 people took part in the study. To take part, they must have already been treated with first-line chemotherapy. Also, their cancer must have shrunk or not grown with this treatment. They were then treated with either avelumab maintenance treatment plus best supportive care or best supportive care alone. Best supportive care means treatments that help improve symptoms and quality of life. These treatments do not affect the cancer directly and can include medicines to relieve pain.

What were the results?

Researchers found that people treated with avelumab maintenance treatment plus best supportive care lived, on average, 7 months longer than people who received best supportive care alone. People treated with avelumab had more side effects than those not treated with avelumab, but most were not severe. Common side effects with avelumab included persistent tiredness, itchy skin, urinary tract infection, and diarrhea.

What do the results of the study mean?

Results from the JAVELIN Bladder 100 study support the use of avelumab as maintenance treatment for people with advanced urothelial cancer whose cancer has shrunk or not grown with first-line chemotherapy.

Avelumab is approved to treat the condition discussed in this summary. This summary reports the results of a single study. The results of this study may differ from those of other studies. Health professionals should make treatment decisions based on all available evidence, not on the results of a single study. The study described is still ongoing; therefore, the final outcomes of this study may differ from the outcomes described in this summary.

How to say (double-click on the icon to play sound)...

- **Avelumab**: a-VEL-yoo-mab
- **Metastatic**: meh-tuh-STA-tik
- **Urothelial**: yoo-roh-THEE-lee-al
- **Chemotherapy**: kee-mow-THEH-ruh-pee

Who sponsored the study?

The JAVELIN Bladder 100 study was sponsored by Pfizer as part of an alliance between Pfizer and Merck (CrossRef Funder ID: 10.13039/100009945).

What is advanced urothelial cancer?

Urothelial cancer can affect the bladder, the inner part of the kidney that collects urine, or other parts of the urinary tract. The urinary tract is a series of tubes that connect the kidneys to the bladder and the bladder to the outside of the body. Urothelial cancer is called advanced when either:

- It has spread into nearby tissues and cannot be removed with surgery. This is known as **locally advanced cancer**.
- It has spread to other parts of the body. This is known as **metastatic** cancer.

Advanced urothelial cancer can cause symptoms, such as frequent and painful urination, back pain, loss of appetite, and unintended weight loss. It can also cause extreme tiredness. Therefore, it often worsens people's quality of life.

For those with **locally advanced urothelial cancer**, an estimated **38%** of people will still be alive 5 years after their diagnosis.

For **metastatic urothelial cancer**, an estimated **6%** of people will still be alive 5 years after diagnosis.

Advanced urothelial cancer has no known cure.

How is advanced urothelial cancer treated?

Chemotherapy

Chemotherapy is a treatment that uses drugs to attack cancer cells directly. Chemotherapy can help stop the spread of cancer and/or slow its growth.

Best supportive care

These are treatments such as antibiotics, medicines to relieve pain, physical therapy, and emotional support. It may also include supplements to help people get enough nutrition and hydration. Radiation therapy, also known as radiotherapy, can also be given to help control symptoms, such as pain or bleeding.

Chemotherapy is often the first treatment given to people with advanced urothelial cancer. This is known as first-line treatment. First-line chemotherapy has helped shrink or stop many people's cancers. However, chemotherapy cannot be given for a long time because of its side effects.

Before the JAVELIN Bladder 100 study, if the cancer shrank or did not grow after chemotherapy, people with advanced urothelial cancer would not receive more cancer treatment but would have regular visits with their doctor. At these visits, they may have tests (such as blood tests) and scans to help their doctor keep an eye on their cancer. People could also receive other treatments that help to manage their symptoms. These treatments do not affect the cancer directly and are called **best supportive care**. Alternatively, people may receive a different treatment shortly after chemotherapy called **maintenance treatment**. This type of treatment has been shown to work well in people with other cancers, like lung and ovarian cancer. But it had not worked in advanced urothelial cancer, until recently.

Although advanced urothelial cancer can get better or stop growing with chemotherapy, for many people, the cancer will start growing again. This usually happens within a year. Doctors and their patients may then decide on a new treatment plan. This might depend on what the doctor thinks is best for their patient. However, people often become too sick or tired to receive additional treatments. They may also decide that they do not want any more treatment.

Maintenance treatment

This is a treatment that can be given if someone’s cancer stops growing or shrinks with a first-line treatment. Its goal is to delay or prevent the cancer from growing again. It also aims to help people live longer.

How does avelumab work?

- Avelumab is a type of **immunotherapy** that is given as a drip (infusion) into a vein for about an hour every 2 weeks. Avelumab attaches to a protein called PD-L1.
- PD-L1 is found on the surface of cancer cells and some cells of the **immune system**.
- When cancer cells have PD-L1 on their surface, the immune system may not recognize them as harmful. This can prevent cancer cells from being found and destroyed.
- When avelumab attaches to PD-L1, it can help immune cells target and destroy cancer cells.

Immunotherapy

This is a type of treatment that boosts the actions of the immune system to help fight cancer.

Immune system

The immune system is the body’s natural defense system that helps the body fight bacteria and viruses. It can also fight cancer.

Some people can have high levels of PD-L1 on cells in their cancer. These people have what is known as PD-L1-positive (or PD-L1+) cancer.

Immunotherapy can help people with various types of cancer live longer. For some cancers, immunotherapy may work better in people with PD-L1+ cancer. But, in other cancers, PD-L1 levels may not make a big difference.

Several immunotherapies have been approved for the treatment of people with advanced urothelial cancer. These approved immunotherapies can be given if:

- The person cannot receive standard first-line chemotherapy, or
- Their cancer started growing after first-line chemotherapy and they need to try a different treatment.

What did the JAVELIN Bladder 100 study look at?

The JAVELIN Bladder 100 study is a phase 3 clinical trial. Phase 3 trials compare a new treatment with currently available treatments.

Researchers wanted to find out whether avelumab maintenance after first-line chemotherapy could help people with advanced urothelial cancer live longer than best supportive care alone.

JAVELIN Bladder 100 selection criteria and treatments

Treatment continued until:

- The cancer started growing again,
- The person had a severe side effect, or
- The person decided to stop their treatment.

For each group, researchers looked at:

- ❓ How long people lived overall,
- ❓ How long people lived before their cancer started growing again,
- ❓ Any side effects that happened during treatment.

Although people did not need to have PD-L1+ cancer to take part in the study, researchers also wanted to see whether having PD-L1+ cancer affected how well avelumab treatment worked.

Who took part in the study?

A total of **700 people** with advanced urothelial cancer took part. Treatment in the study started 4 to 10 weeks after people had finished first-line chemotherapy.

JAVELIN Bladder 100 study design

Where did the study take place?

This study took place at hospitals in 29 countries across the world:

- | | |
|----------------|--------------------|
| Argentina | Mexico |
| Australia | The Netherlands |
| Belgium | New Zealand |
| Brazil | Norway |
| Canada | Poland |
| Czech Republic | Portugal |
| Denmark | Republic of Korea |
| France | Russian Federation |
| Greece | Serbia |
| Hong Kong | Spain |
| Hungary | Sweden |
| India | Taiwan |
| Israel | United Kingdom |
| Italy | United States |
| Japan | |

What were the results of the JAVELIN Bladder 100 study?

Initial results from the JAVELIN Bladder 100 study were collected in October 2019

1 Researchers found that, on average, people in **Group 1** lived 7 months longer than in **Group 2**

2 More people in **Group 1** were still alive 1 year after starting the study compared with **Group 2**

71%

of people who were treated with avelumab plus best supportive care were still alive after 1 year

58%

of people who were treated with best supportive care alone were still alive after 1 year

3 Researchers also found that, on average, people in **Group 1** lived longer without their cancer starting to grow again than in **Group 2**

4

Researchers also looked at people who had PD-L1+ cancers in both groups

They found that on average, these people also lived longer with avelumab plus best supportive care than with best supportive care alone. In addition, on average, people treated with avelumab also lived longer without their cancer starting to grow again than with best supportive care alone. But people who did not have PD-L1+ cancer also lived longer, on average, with avelumab treatment than without it.

What were the most common side effects seen in the study?

Researchers looked at any **side effects** that people had during the study. These side effects could have been caused by the study treatment or by other reasons. These reasons could include the cancer itself, other illnesses, or other medicines.

Side effects

Side effects are generally undesirable effects that could possibly be related to a treatment.

In Group 1 (avelumab plus best supportive care), **98%** of people had at least 1 side effect.

In Group 2 (best supportive care alone), **78%** of people had at least 1 side effect.

Only a few of these were **severe side effects**. The most common side effects are shown below. These are side effects that happened in more than 15% of people in **Group 1**. The percentage of people with the same side effects in **Group 2** is also shown.

Severe side effects

Severe side effects limit someone's ability to look after themselves, need hospital treatment, or have a risk of death.

The most common side effects in the study

Group 1

Avelumab + best supportive care

Group 2

Best supportive care alone

Persistent tiredness (fatigue)

18%

Severe in 2%

7%

Severe in 1%

The most common side effects in the study continued...

Group 1

Avelumab + best supportive care

Group 2

Best supportive care alone

Itchy skin (pruritus)

17%
Severe in less than 1%

2%
None were severe

Urinary tract infection

17%
Severe in 4%

10%
Severe in 3%

Diarrhea

17%
Severe in 1%

5%
Severe in less than 1%

Joint stiffness (arthralgia)

16%
Severe in 1%

6%
None were severe

Physical weakness or lack of energy (asthenia)

16%
None were severe

6%
Severe in 1%

The most common side effects in the study continued....

Because avelumab stimulates the body’s immune system, avelumab may also cause immune cells to target normal tissues in the body, which causes so-called immune-related side effects.

In the study, these types of side effects happened in 29% of people in **Group 1** and included thyroid disorders, rash, and itchy skin. These were severe in 7% of people.

In **Group 1**, 12% of people stopped avelumab maintenance treatment because of side effects.

2 people had side effects that led to their death:

- 1 person had a life-threatening reaction (sepsis) to a urinary tract infection after 11 doses of avelumab
- 1 person had a stroke 100 days after 1 dose of avelumab and after their cancer started growing again

The doctors caring for these people thought that these side effects were related to avelumab treatment.

What do the results of the JAVELIN Bladder 100 study mean?

In the JAVELIN Bladder 100 study:

People with advanced urothelial cancer whose cancer had shrunk or not grown with first-line chemotherapy took part. People who were treated with avelumab maintenance lived longer, on average, than those who were treated with best supportive care alone.

People who received avelumab maintenance also lived longer, on average, without their cancer starting to grow again.

People who had PD-L1+ cancers also lived longer, on average, with avelumab. Avelumab also helped people live longer whether or not they had PD-L1+ cancer.

People in the avelumab group had more side effects than people in the best supportive care group. This was expected because people in the best supportive care group only received treatments to help improve their symptoms and not treat their cancer. Most side effects with avelumab were not severe. They were also similar to those seen in previous avelumab studies.

Side effects can happen during treatment or even after treatment is finished. More education is needed to teach people how to look out for side effects and where to report them. This can help doctors decide how to help people and to make these decisions more quickly.

The study results support the use of **avelumab** as maintenance treatment for people with advanced **urothelial** cancer that has shrunk or not grown with first-line **chemotherapy**. The results of the JAVELIN Bladder 100 study led to **avelumab** maintenance becoming a standard treatment for these people.

What are the next steps?

The JAVELIN Bladder 100 study is still ongoing. Researchers are continuing to look at people with advanced urothelial cancer in the study to understand the effects of avelumab over a longer time. They are also looking at:

- ? The effects of avelumab in several groups of people. These groups include people who have different characteristics, cancer features, or treatment backgrounds.
- ? How avelumab maintenance affects people's quality of life.

Where can I find more information on this study?

Original article

The original article 'Avelumab maintenance therapy for advanced or metastatic urothelial carcinoma' was published in *The New England Journal of Medicine* (Powles T, et al. *N. Engl. J. Med.* 383(13), 1218–1230 [2020])

You can read the full article at:

<https://www.nejm.org/doi/full/10.1056/NEJMoa2002788>

Trial registration site

You can read more about the phase 3 JAVELIN Bladder 100 study at the following study registration websites:

- <https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/NCT02603432>
- <https://www.clinicaltrialsregister.eu/ctr-search/search?query=2015-003262-86>

For more information on clinical studies in general, please visit:

<https://www.clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/about-studies/learn>
<http://www.cancerresearchuk.org/about-cancer/find-a-clinical-trial/what-clinical-trials-are>

Educational resources

You can read more about bladder cancer and urothelial cancer at the following websites:

<https://www.cancer.net/cancer-types/bladder-cancer>
<https://www.cancer.org/cancer/bladder-cancer.html>

Patient guidelines on bladder cancer and urothelial cancer from NCCN are available at:

<https://www.nccn.org/guidelines/guidelines-detail?category=1&id=1417>

Acknowledgements

The authors of this article thank the people who participated in this study and their families, as well as the investigators, co-investigators, and staff at each of the clinical sites. The authors also thank Stephanie Chisolm from the Bladder Cancer Advocacy Network for her review of this summary.

Financial & competing interests disclosure

Full author disclosure information can be found in the original article.

Writing support for this summary was provided by Abhijith Thippeswamy of ClinicalThinking and funded by Pfizer and Merck (CrossRef Funder ID: 10.13039/100009945).

Author affiliations

¹Barts Cancer Institute, Experimental Cancer Medicine Centre, Queen Mary University of London, St Bartholomew's Hospital, London, UK; ²Sungkyunkwan University Samsung Medical Center, Seoul, Korea; ³Centre Jean Bernard Clinique Victor Hugo, Le Mans, France; ⁴Medical Oncology Unit, Azienda Ospedaliera S Maria, Terni, Italy; ⁵Department of Medical Oncology Hospital Universitario Virgen del Rocío, Sevilla, Spain; ⁶Department of Clinical Medicine, Macquarie University, Sydney, NSW, Australia; ⁷Medical Oncology, University General Hospital of Patras, Patras, Greece; ⁸Institute for Oncology and Radiology of Serbia, Belgrade, Serbia; ⁹Department of Medical Oncology, AZ KLINA, Brasschaat, Belgium; ¹⁰Patient Area Pelvic Cancer, Theme Cancer, Karolinska University Hospital and Department of Oncology–Pathology, Karolinska Institute, Solna, Sweden; ¹¹Gustave Roussy, INSERMU981 Université Paris–Saclay, Villejuif, France; ¹²Princess Margaret Cancer Center, University Health Network, Toronto, ON, Canada; ¹³Department of Urology, Yamagata University Faculty of Medicine, Yamagata, Japan; ¹⁴State Institution of Healthcare Regional Clinical Oncology Dispensary, Omsk, Russia; ¹⁵Hematology/Oncology, Weill Cornell Medicine, Englander Institute for Precision Medicine, Sandra and Edward Meyer Cancer Center, New York, NY, USA; ¹⁶Department of Medical Oncology, Beth Israel Deaconess Medical Center, Harvard Medical School, Boston, MA, USA; ¹⁷Inova Schar Cancer Institute, Fairfax, VA, USA; ¹⁸Yale Cancer Center, New Haven, CT, USA; ¹⁹Pfizer, Cambridge, MA, USA; ²⁰Pfizer, Groton, CT, USA; ²¹Pfizer, Porto Salvo, Portugal; ²²Pfizer, La Jolla, CA, USA; ²³Department of Medicine, Division of Medical Oncology, University of Washington, Clinical Research Division, Fred Hutchinson Cancer Research Center, Seattle, WA, USA